

A new record for the Turkish mycota: *Xylaria filiformis*

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Abstract: *Xylaria filiformis* is recorded for the first time from Turkey.

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Introduction

In November 2006, during routine field trips to different localities of Çanakkale, many samples of fungi were collected. According to the checklists by Sesli & Denchev (2005), the ascomycete *Xylaria filiformis* (*Xylariaceae*) was found to be a new record for Turkey. This taxon was identified with the help of the description and illustrations by Breitenbach & Kränzlin (1984). Specimens of the material cited below are deposited in the Herbarium of Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University in Çanakkale and in the first author's personal collection.

Result

Xylaria filiformis (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) Fr., Summa Veg. Scand., Sectio Post. (Stockholm), p. 382 (1849). **Fig. 1**

Fruiting bodies (stromata) single to cespitose, filiform, irregularly compressed, erect, 20–80 (–100) × 0.5–2 mm, sinuous, unbranched, rarely forked, whitish to almost black in the conidial stage and the tips orange-brown, central to upper part thickened in the ascus stage and warty-tuberculate from the embedded perithecia, brownish to brown-black, inner plectenchyma of the stroma white. **Spores** elliptical,

flattened on one side, smooth, brown, with 1–3 guttules and a germination cleft along the whole length, 12–17 × 6–7.5 µm. **Asci** 117–125 × 9 µm, eight-spored, spores uniseriate.

Specimen examined: **TURKEY:** Çanakkale, Ezine, around the Kara Menderes stream, 39°51'48.6" N, 26°18'46.2" E, alt. 39 m, on herbaceous debris, 5 Nov 2006 (B. Dulger no. 1212).

Discussion

Mature ascus stages of *Xylaria filiformis* occur especially in late fall. According to Breitenbach & Kränzlin (1984), small forms of *X. filiformis* are very similar to *X. carpophila*, which, however, is found on beech (*Fagus*) cupules.

Slender forms of *X. hypoxylon* sometimes superficially resemble *X. filiformis*, but the former species is usually much more robust than the latter. They are also separable on ascospore characters. Moreover, *X. hypoxylon* occurs on wood, whereas *X. filiformis* grows on herbaceous debris and leaves (e.g., Rogers & Samuels 1986), just like our collection. While the stromata of *X. filiformis* are usually glabrous in their lower part, the basal part of the stromata in our material is distinctly hairy (Fig. 1).

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Fig. 1. Fruiting body (stroma) of *Xylaria filiformis* in the conidial stage. Bar = 5 mm

The spore diameter of *X. filiformis* is apparently rather variable. For example, Breitenbach & Kränzlin (1984) give $12.5-17 \times 5-6.5 \mu\text{m}$, but the spore diameter of our specimen was $12-17 \times 6-7.5 \mu\text{m}$.

References

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